

In situ isotopic ^{238}U - ^{234}U - ^{232}Th - ^{230}Th dating analysis using LA-ICPMS

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U-Th (or ^{238}U - ^{234}U - ^{232}Th - ^{230}Th) dating is frequently used to determine the timing of Earth's geological, environmental, and biotic processes from materials formed a few years in the past to over 800 thousand years (ka). Here we present high sensitivity, *in situ* determinations of carbonate U and Th isotope ratios and ages using laser ablation inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (LA-ICPMS). Through the use of a "Jet" interface setup and the optimization of LA and ICP-MS conditions, the detection efficiency has been improved to a yield of 1-2%. A well characterized triple-spike (TS) ^{229}Th - ^{233}U - ^{236}U tracer was added to the laser generated aerosol by means of a desolvation nebulization system (DSN). The TS ($^{236}\text{U}/^{233}\text{U}$) and TS ($^{233}\text{U}/^{229}\text{Th}$) intensity ratios were used to monitor and correct for instrumental mass discrimination and U/Th elemental fractionation effects, respectively. The mass load was increased step by step using circular laser with spot diameters of 16, 24, 44, 60, and 90 μm , with constant repetition rates of 20 Hz and a scan speed of 5 $\mu\text{m}/\text{sec}$. Through the careful tuning and optimization by LA analyses on the standard of NIST SRM 612 with its $^{238}\text{U}/^{232}\text{Th}$ ratios approximately to 1, the mass discrimination for the measured TS ($^{236}\text{U}/^{233}\text{U}$) was slightly below the certificate ratios (0.9796), but in line with the $^{238}\text{U}/^{235}\text{U}$ ratio obtained by laser ablation for the NIST SRM 612 (0.9705). U/Th isotopic ratios for the TS ($^{233}\text{U}/^{229}\text{Th}$) were also close to the reference values (1.0150), while the laser generated aerosol exhibited a slightly lower ratio (0.9785) for NIST SRM 612 ($^{238}\text{U}/^{232}\text{Th}$). Yet, analysis of a flowstone sample in secular equilibrium, collected from Northern Calcareous Alps, resulted in activity ratios of 1.011 ± 0.066 ($2\sigma_m$) for $^{230}\text{Th}/^{238}\text{U}$, indicating that laser ablation data can be generated with good accuracy. A 2-sigma precision of $\pm 3\%$ from only 5 μg of carbonate mass (10 fg of ^{238}U) for a 190-ka stalagmite, could be achieved. This approach allows for the reconstruction of high spatial age profiles for young carbonates with age > 5 ka, and could be applied for the better constrain the timing of past climatic events.